

A Graphical Vision of Aesthetics of Al-Quds Architecture through the Digital Technology

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Abstract

This study addresses the possibilities of digital technology in the creativity of an applied graphic study of the aesthetics of Jerusalem architecture through the Islamic and Christian architectural monuments of Al-Quds city, because of its great religious and historical importance

The study was conducted on a sample of Islamic and Christian antiquities in the city of Jerusalem by collecting archaeological data that represent successive time periods, redesigning and drawing through addition and deletion as a work of art from a graphic perspective, and merging them with the effect of chisel engraving technology used in traditional graphic arts.

Analysis was done on the samples of artworks that have been processed on the monuments of Jerusalem through the digital technology used and the methods of deletion and addition in terms of font and color usages in the printed artwork.

The most frequently used analytical and evaluation criteria on the artistic and visual elements of these research technical experiments, the effect of this on developing the performance and artistic direction of the researcher, and the possibility of applying this to other archaeological sites. It was a case study of Jerusalem and the role of graphic art in showing the artistic and aesthetic values of that city.

It was relied on using the criteria for visual analysis and evaluation of the produced works, and the most important aesthetic and visual Art aspects resulting from these visional artworks for the monuments of Al-Quds city.

Keywords- *Artistic vision, Al-Quds architecture, Digital technology*

I. INTRODUCTION

The technological development has recently brought with it the prospect of a transition to a new civilized era, where it reflects a tremendous/ dramatic transformation in communication technology, curriculum of cultures and information systems. This development has also unleashed wide trends to apply digital technology and using it in the design programs as well as Digital and Media Arts.

This new trend does not establish its applications and programs to brave the way for digital arts without the acquisition of a set of data that begins with shaping the phenomena of the development of graphical and graphic software technology and ends with creating a network that defines new functions of visual language and image and audio files.

These digital arts reflect in fact the essence of the digital age thus become closer to the science, which employs many of the results of other sciences in the field of developing and producing a digital image that expresses the essence of materialized and cognitive civilization.

The aim of digital arts is to reproduce reality itself through controlling the image and transferring the real-life from its place limitations into virtual reality metaphors and carried from other imaginary places.

This research examined the possibilities of digital technology in the creativity of an applied graphic study of the aesthetics of Jerusalem architecture. Al-Quds Al-Sharif has been selected to apply the experiment on its monuments, because of its great importance not only at the level of the Arab world but also at the world level, too.

There are no researchers or artists who dealt with the aesthetic aspect of the effects of Jerusalem through the digital graphics processing of the most important Islamic architectural monuments inside Al Aqsa Mosque/Al-Haram Al-Sharif and the Christian architectural monuments in the Old City. They dealt with it from a graphical perspective through the aesthetics of architectural and decorative style and incorporated by the impact of the Burin Line Engraving technique used in traditional graphic arts. This experience addresses on color and calligraphy as two important elements of the artwork.

The research dealt with a proposal to design an encyclopedia of the researcher's art collection, in an attempt to record part of the most important monuments of Jerusalem in a modern graphic way. Whereas, these accomplishments were dealt with through digital processing by deletion, addition, and analysis of the architectural monument's textures, and redrawing them using the Burin Line Engraving technique through a philosophical vision of integrating history and art with technology. The digital printmaking art has been evolved through the interest that the graphic artists have shown, where digital art techniques have combined with traditional graphic arts techniques to produce a homogeneous mix of many outstanding artworks.

This research dealt with an analytical study of a number of artworks of the researcher out of 40 artworks that have been produced through the use of digital technology using a number of pictures for the features of the architecture of Jerusalem.

This comes through the Digital Art Techniques, and its role in the contemporary graphic arts, especially the Digital Printmaking and its multiple outputs of the aesthetics of the design structure of digital graphic arts, where graphic arts is one of the arts in which technology is a key factor, both constructively and aesthetically. As a result, this art affects the innovative thought and artistic creativity of human beings, because his artistic printing techniques are distinguished by their special aesthetic values that are characterized by a high degree of visual excitement, which in turn stimulates intellectual excitement.

A. Research Problem

Although traditional engraving and printing techniques have high artistic value, they are unable to keep up with the rapidly evolving digital technologies in the graphic industry. As a result, it was necessary to search for new digital technologies that contribute, among other things, to preserve the artistic and architectural heritage in general and the heritage of the city of Jerusalem in particular and at the same time meets the rhythm of the times, the speed of achievement and diversity of visions, as well as meet the artist's tendency towards creativity and innovation, and develop the aesthetic longing for the recipient.

B. The Importance of the Research:

1. The research contributes to the adaptation of digital technology to record architectural and artistic monuments as graphic artwork.
2. The research contributes to clarifying the technical and applied aspects that establish the visual processing of the monuments of Jerusalem in particular and the Arab antiquities in the Middle East in general.
3. The research contributes to the identification of more accurate details in the architecture of Jerusalem, including the architectural heritage and distinctive Islamic and Christian decoration.

C. Research Objectives:

1. Developing contemporary graphic insights to record architectural monuments into graphic artworks using digital technology.
2. Linking classical printing techniques with digital printing technology for graphic designs in the educational process.
3. Using the artistic product as illustrations to design a proposed encyclopedia about the relics of Jerusalem.

D. (Limitations of the Study):

The limits of the research are determined in the following: -

1. Spatial Boundaries: Islamic and Christian Monuments in Jerusalem.
2. Time boundaries: the heritage of the city of Jerusalem, which extends for a period of time exceeding 2000 years..

II. METHODOLOGY

This research used the applied descriptive-analytical approach.

A. Artistic Vision

Vision is defined linguistically according to Al-Jammi glossary of meanings as seeing things properly, and the vision of the eye and the heart, too. It also includes in its concept many of meanings, such as perceptions and attitudes, aspirations, hopes and mental assumptions, and is the basis of any development the institution seeks to achieve, through cooperation between the members of the institution and their commitment to their work, and the vision must be clear, simple and concise [1].

The vision is the angle of view of the artist and how the artist senses the universe, the world, and life, and it is also considered as the vision that the artist uses to look at life. On the other hand, it is the strategic perspective of the artist's path or viewpoint, the verification of his art, and the quality of the innovation and renovation he deals with. This leaves a distinctive fingerprint, sometimes difficult to understand, or maybe astonishing. However, it is an expression of the small details in the life of the human being and the harbingers, obsessions, thoughts, aspirations, and dreams.

There is no doubt that the artistic vision is one of the cognitive processes for human beings, which are related to the activities of thinking, sensation, and perception, through which one gains a huge amount of information and experiences, throughout the period of his interaction with the

environment and society around him.

Therefore, artistic vision "is the perception of the world surrounding the artist in his own and special understanding, whether this world is a form, idea, social event, or scientific information, it serves as the framework that surrounds and guides the artist's effectiveness."

Dr. Hoda Zaki also indicates about the vision: "The vision requires to look at things first, and the eye is the device that receives the images of things, and we all have eyes, but we do not all own an artistic vision. Thus, we ought to train our sense of sight to meditate, look, and observe nature. Meditation occurs by looking at things and noticing exceptional things about them like the axial lines in the system of construction or formation. Changes in color, for example, or in other formative relationships are recognized through the system of natural formation law."

It is a fundamental postulate in the practice of artistic vision that it does not come from nil, but rather it is a process of integrating the artist's talent, creativity, cognitive, and sentimental ability.

Sources of artistic vision include three directions:

- Nature which is the main source.
- The national and international artistic cultural heritage.
- Experimentation as an updated source arise from/ be consequent on technological and eventual developments.

Experimentation in modern times has become one of the sources of artistic vision, as it is a process that combines the continuity of the initiative thinking, the divergent thinking, or the creative thinking, which achieve new concepts unprecedented in the search for artistic values in any of the Fine Art masterpieces [2].

B. Jerusalem architecture

There is no doubt that the city of Jerusalem has respect and glorification among peoples of different countries and religions, and this originates from the facts and spiritual events the Holy City went through. Jerusalem is located in the center of Palestine, 29 kilometers away from the Dead Sea from the east, and 50 kilometers away from the Mediterranean Sea from the west adding to that the fact that it is above about 750 meters sea level.

Historically, the city of Jerusalem has been subjected to demolition and construction for more than eighteen times, and it is a mountainous city with ancient borders which were based on five mountains. The first mountain is (Moorea) where Al-Haram Al-Sharif, topped by the Dome of the Rock, is located on, and Al-Aqsa mosque is located on its south side and Al Buraq Wall on its western side, which forms part of the Old City Wall. The rest of the five mountains are Mount (Ophel), Mount (Sehion), Mount (Akra) and Mount (Bizetna) which includes the hill that extends from Bab Hatta to Bab al-Amoud. With the expansion of settlements, the Holy City started to include (Mount Al-Zaytun) in East Jerusalem, (Mount Al-Masharef), also called Mashhad, in the north of the Holy City, (Mount Qatamon) in the south of the city, and (Mount Mukabar) in the southeast of the city.

Palestinian Islamic architecture followed in its beginnings Syrian architecture and some Byzantine excerpts, especially in the Umayyad period. The Jerusalem architecture inherited the local constructional style, and its features were decorated with stone carvings and fine mosaic surfaces.

As for the religious monuments, the mosque has been the most well-cared of since the entry of the Caliph Al-Rashid Omar. The first mosques were built using the inherited local style, and its design was influenced by the scheme of the Umayyad Mosque and the scheme of the Prophetic type was chosen, which includes the rectangular sanctuary built perpendicular to the direction of the qibla which is surrounded by Aspects. The architecture of the Al-Aqsa Mosque may be a typical example of this, despite the subsequent changes that have taken place.

The Fatimid and Ayyubid Islamic periods have witnessed the development of new architecture and stone arts and the rise of their new elements. This era witnessed changes in which facades were of exceptional importance, unlike in previous eras. This historical role, for the first time, can be without exaggeration the initiative to make the styles of architecture in the Levant, Palestine, and Egypt unite and continue to these days. It has been also one of the strongest architectural styles in Islamic architecture sober, influential and private, which depends mainly on the architecture of stone and architectural elements that the material exists [3].

C. Digital Technology

Linguistically, Technology which comes from "perfecting" means controlling, adjusting, and mastering things.[4]

“ وَتَرَى الْجِبَالَ تَحْسَبُهَا جَامِدَةً وَهِيَ تَمُرُّ مَرَّ السَّحَابِ صُنِعَ اللَّهُ الَّذِي أَنْفَقَ كُلَّ شَيْءٍ إِنَّهُ خَبِيرٌ بِمَا تَفْعَلُونَ ” سورة النمل الآية (88)

"Perfected" in verse: "And you see the mountains, thinking them rigid, while they will pass as the passing of clouds. [It is] the work of Allah, who perfected all things. Indeed, He is Acquainted with that which you do" (88) Surat An-Naml The Holy Quran.[5] "Perfected" thing: mastered, and brought it to a completed picture.

Technically, the term "Technology" derives from the Greek word for art that means two aspects from Monroe's point of view:

The first aspect is the sum of the actual skills and processes themselves that the working individual went through to reach an already well-defined existing product, while the second aspect is theoretical knowledge or science that grows and develops in connection with skills. It can also be represented in the abilities and processes that enter into art and involve creativity in the aesthetic and utilitarian aspects and all that has the ability to invent in thought works to find new functional or decorative features and include the basic artistic creations of each medium and the ability to use them including arts tools [6].

Technology concept; It is defined as the systematic application of scientific knowledge or any other kind of knowledge in order to achieve practical tasks. It is also an integrated organization that includes: human, machine, ideas, opinions, working methods, and management, so that all these components work together within a single framework. It is also defined as Systematic processing of art or all means used to produce things necessary for human comfort and continuity of existence, and it is a technical way to perform or accomplish scientific purposes. Fine arts techniques concept is used on three things:

1. Total methods followed in the use of some machines, tools, or materials such as techniques of playing on one of the musical instruments or techniques of engraving on plaster.
2. Total methods specialized for a particular type of fine art.
3. Total methods specialized for a particular artist, writer or poet [7].

Technology is defined as the technical aspect of design, which is the absolute necessity that shows us how the designer should be in contact with sophisticated scientific seminars and all modern discoveries and theories that achieve the pleasure and benefit of that era. Thus, it means the systematic application of scientific knowledge, and means tools, instruments, and materials resulting from the application of scientific knowledge as products of processes. Computer technologies are an ideal example of the interaction between processes and their products.

1. **Burin Line Engraving manual technique;**

This technique emerged during the fifteenth century in both Italy and Germany and the Italian artist Antonio De Poliaolo (1429 - 1498) was the first to set a fixed standard for the technique of Burin Line Engraving on metal for the purposes of printing and publishing in Europe [8]. It has a great feature which is the ability to work with much better details and more accurate than the ones in the technique of engraving on wood. Burin Line Engraving lines help to serve the design in one way or another by studying people, for example, and how the lines resulting from the engraving help to show the degrees of light and dark, where the engraved parallel lines are used to achieve a variety of shades and light as the density and spacing of those lines in some areas had the greatest impact on the identification and confirmation of shade and light spots Fig.1, 2.

Figure 1: Burin Line Engraving manual technique on Copper

Figure 2: Details for artist Printmaker Apostle Bartholomew, Burin Line Engraving manual technique on Copper, 1589

2. **Digital processing software and techniques used in the practical aspect of research;**

With the development of computer technologies and entering the digital revolution came the term digital art which is the reliance on computers as a tool to communicate the visual message. It is also a broad term that includes the works and practices used by digital technology in professional ways, as an important element to flourish the concept of creativity.

Since the 1970s, digital art has become a prominent medium of modern media. With the development of technology and the availability of various digital design programs, digital art has become one of the newest and most beautiful arts, receiving the attention of various groups, including amateur designers and photographers.

Digital art is perceived as the concept of transforming classical and fine art through the computer to more professional images, and this explains the success reached and accomplishing a stage that makes it a key element in various fields wherever we go.

One of the most important types of digital art is (Photo manipulation) [9], where the artist

integrates and deals with images by adding or deleting through the layers. This type is one of the most famous, appealing, and creative digital art. It is also resulted out of choosing different images to be merged and dealt with by deleting or adding effects and adjustments to them, producing a magnificent fantasy painting reflecting the imagination of the designer.

The research has benefited from the different techniques, including what is the twin of classical techniques in the field of graphic, especially Burin Line Engraving technique, which depends on the intersections of lines horizontally and vertically in order to reach the same effect of the traditional Burin Line Engraving technique. It was the technique that the researcher has used in terms of experimentation on the monuments of Jerusalem to employ the effect of Burin Line Engraving in order to convert images of Jerusalem's monuments into masterpieces that will record and perpetuate the most important monuments of Jerusalem. He has also applied that product to the book of monuments of Jerusalem.

The research relied directly on the image because of its importance as a visual and communicative element, and its aesthetic value. He also relied on several factors to deal with the image of the monuments of Jerusalem through the use of the Bitmap system, in which the image is divided into several points that represent a map of compact rows which is more like pieces of a mosaic. Each point reflects a color that has its own position within that map, which is called Resolution, and the fewer the number of points in the image, the lower the resolution of the image.

The research relied on the use of Adobe Photoshop program, which is one of the most important applications in the processing of bitmap, the field of drawing, and computer design. It is also a program with a high ability in the processing of images and effects. The researcher reviews the phases that he adopted to reach a set of artworks which rely on a large number of processing steps in order to convert the photograph of the elements of Jerusalem monuments into artworks that will be put on record for the benefit of these important architectural monuments, and these stages are:

1. Raise the efficiency of the original image through the Image Size option to 300 Pixels / Inch.
2. Use the Mode command, which is used to change the color scheme of the image.
3. A list of Adjustment commands for color adjustments, tonal gradations, and color balance.

The list consists of the following:

- The Levels command adjusts the color balance by specifying the pixel units distribution for individual color channels.
- The Curves command provides up to 14 control points to adjust highlights, midtones, and shadows for individual channels.
- The Exposure command adjusts the tonality by performing calculations in a linear color space. Exposure is mainly used with HDR images.
- The Vibrance command adjusts the color saturation so that the truncation decreases.
- The Photo Filter command performs color adjustments by simulating the effects of using the filter factor Kodak Wratten or Fuji in front of the viewfinder.
- The Color Balance command changes the overall color mix in an image.

- The Hue / Saturation command sets the hue, saturation, and color brightness values for the entire image or each color component.
 - The Match Color command matches the color from one image to another, from layer to layer, and from a selection in the image to another selection in the same or another image. It also adjusts the brightness and color range and neutralizes the unreal colors in the image.
 - The Replace Color command replaces the color specified in an image with new color values.
 - The Selective Color command adjusts the amount of process colors in individual color components.
 - The Channel Mixer command adjusts the color channel and performs color adjustment processes that are difficult to apply using other color adjustment tools [10].
4. Applying the digital Burin Line Engraving technique in Photoshop program used the Action Engraving lines Photoshop tool which is a series of predefined steps that can be applied to files. These steps can be applied to any file by converting the image to a Burin Line Engraving technique, to obtain various effects of overlapping lines in order to create a graphic artwork based on visual vision. Here is the problem of the research and the resulting solutions and results of it, where the researcher depends on converting images to a graphic processing with the use of Burin Line Engraving technique by dividing the image into several layers with the analysis of the image into a group of silhouettes in which wavy-curved lines overlap vertically, horizontally, and pivotally. Fig. 3. Sabil Qaitbay at Masjid al-Aqsa.
 5. The rectangular, square, and circle geometric shapes were used with the Paint Bucket tool (G), a tool in Photoshop toolkit specialized for color fill for shapes.
 6. Use the Blending mode feature from the Layers menu where blending modes are used to edit digital images and computer graphics to determine how to blend two layers together. The default blending mode in most applications is to hide the bottom layer by covering it with everything that exists in the top layer. However, since each pixel has a numeric representation, there are many ways to mix two or more layers. Here comes the experimentation phase in the artwork where a number of image effects are used from the researcher's manual artwork and the use of the merge feature with up to 40 layers in some works. Each layer requires the researcher to choose the best visualizations for merging and experimentation until the artwork reaches the creative stage that the researcher seeks.

Figure 3: Effect of Digital Burin Line Engraving manual technique

Detailed digital processing of The Sabil Qaitbay

D. Philosophy of architecture in Jerusalem (the doors of Jerusalem - mosques - churches - minarets - domes - Sabils - roads and streets of the Old City).

Jerusalem is the city of God, one of the holiest cities in the world, and it means in all the names given to it throughout its long history: holiness, purity, and exclusion from sins.

Jerusalem is an elevated city on the mountains, where anyone who is destined Palestine can reach it. Anyone who cares about Jerusalem, its history, the nations, and civilizations that have lived on its land since ancient times, must recognize the treasures of this city, the monuments, and the great remnants that it contains. These kinds of information can be used to understand the city's nature and its geographical and strategic location. If we were lucky to recognize this reality, then we had understood the past and have overseen the future.

The ancient name of Jerusalem (the city of peace, Jerusalem) comes back from the Canaanite Jebusites, the ancestors of the Arabs who established this city. This was confirmed through the letters of Tel Amarna that were sent to Egypt during the reign of Akhenaten, and then the name was re-used by the Hasmoneans. The Arabs, however, regarded this city with great esteem, first using its Roman-Byzantine name (Elijah) and then calling it Al-Quds, Bayt Al-Maqdis [11].

There is no doubt that there are great efforts of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan through the Hashemite guardianship of the Islamic and Christian holy sites in Bayt Al-Maqdis to preserve those holy sites, which are witnessing a large Judaization movement by the Israeli occupier.

There is no doubt that there are general basic principles adhered to the scheme of the Islamic city architecturally, regardless of the time and place in which they arise, and that there are special characteristics and principles of artistic, architectural, social, and environmental that vary depending on time and place. In the Holy City of Al-Quds Al-Sharif, the scheme took into account these principles and features, since it considered that religion has a fundamental relationship in the architectural planning of the city of Jerusalem. The mosque should be the main center of the planning unit, from which the city's architectural structure is branched out. Consequently, Al-Aqsa Mosque was the main focus in the planning of this city. Adding to that, the harmony with the environment within one spirituality and the simplicity of planning that inspires psychological comfort and architectural beauty.

The most prominent feature of Jerusalem's art was the formation of new architectural elements and the creation of expressions and artistic objects.

This came as a result of benefiting from the experiences, ways, and methods of the art of buildings of other civilizations such as Sasanian, Greek, Byzantine, and Islamic, whose elements and architectural objects had a notable impact on the beautiful architectural character of this city.

The Old City's landmarks are one of the most beautiful and timeless monuments in the history of human civilization, and occupy an important and prestigious place on the UNESCO World Heritage List [12].

One of the key features of Al-Quds city is its character is that it preserves its architectural and decorative components closely linked to the customs, traditions, and culture of its Arab inhabitants. Some of these components are the solidarity residential neighborhoods, and the main services like

markets, mosques, schools, and health services which are linked to residential districts and not separated from them [13].

It also maintains its cultural, artistic, environmental, and architectural heritage, to ensure that no weird elements are introduced, or no weird part is removed, while constantly maintaining it.

The research dealt with models of the monuments of Bayt Al-Maqdis, which are difficult to confine in scientific research because they need an encyclopedia. However, the aim is to make use of modern design software technology to help record the architectural monument of Jerusalem not as a photograph, but as a work of Fine Art, hence the models will be addressed through the architectural division of the monuments of Bayt Al-Maqdis and the Old City architectural.

It is the applied side using digital processing to use images of the monuments of architecture in Bayt Al-Maqdis and converted into digital artworks. In this theoretical study of the art exhibition comes the importance of focusing on recording the fourth dimension in Jerusalem architecture. This dimension is a time dimension recorded by these distinctive artistic architectural landmarks throughout the history of Jerusalem, and the Al-Aqsa Mosque has about 200 landmarks located within its geographical boundaries, ranging from mosques, buildings, domes, and Subul of Water, terraces, corridors, schools, niches, pulpits, minarets, doors, wells, and libraries [14].

This city includes the tomb of Jesus, the path of Pains, Qubbat as-Sakhrah, the place of Al-Miraj, the Marwani Mosque, where the Holy Prophet led the prophets in prayer, and many doors, subul, domes, and minarets. Then, Muslims came to the blessed city through caliphs, sultans, and kings.

Since recording many of the Arab monuments with an artistic vision through the Orientalist artists headed by David Roberts through Lithography printing technology, we nowadays need to focus on seeing the monuments, but to get acquainted with them, their aesthetics, and the role they played in the life of Bayt Al-Maqdis throughout history. Consequently, it should be turned into artworks through the digital processing of the shape of the Islamic and Christian monuments of Jerusalem, and directed by digital printing.

The research also aimed to reflect this artistic experience on the students of graphic design to enrich their creative process through looking at things differently and using diverse philosophies considering this aim as is a prime purpose of the research.

1. The Gates of the Old City

Al-Quds wall was built during the Canaanite era, but it was destroyed several times by the invading armies, and the last destruction of this wall was by King Isa al-Ayyubi in 1226, for fear of strengthening the crusader armies in case of occupying the city. Then, the Ottoman Sultan Suleiman Al-qanuni came and ordered to reconstruct the existing wall, and kept all tax revenues in Palestine for five years for the reconstruction process. The wall takes the form of a trapezoid, with a circumference of 2.5 miles, a length of 3930 feet from the north, 2754 feet from the east, 3245 feet from the south, 2086 feet from the west, and it has thirty-four towers, and both Al-Laqlaq and sulfur towers are the most famous ones.

Jerusalem has seven open doors so far, namely the gate of Al-Amoud, the gate of the As-Sahirah, the gate of Al-Asbat, the gate of Al-Magharibah, the gate of the Prophet David, the Gate Al-Khalil, and the Iron Gate. There are also four closed gates namely the Golden Gate (Mercy Gate - repentance) which is located in the eastern wall, and Bab al-Wahid which is located in the southern wall. Samples of

these gates will be examined by historical and aesthetic study and how the gates' photographs were processed into a graphical artwork based on a combination of the traditional digital and Burin Line Engraving techniques [15].

Bab al-Amud, is one of the most beautiful and richest gates of Jerusalem in the architectural and decorative aspect. It is located in the northern wall of the old city wall which leads to two main streets, Khan al-Zayt and al-Wad road, which crosses the old city from north to south, and it is now known to the people of Jerusalem as the A-Wad.

It was named the Gate of A-Wad according to a column that existed in the Roman period (2nd century AD), and the door has two levels. The highest level is Ottoman built during the reign of Suleiman Al-Qanuni in 944-1537 / 1538, which is the current door. The lower level is a triumph arc of which only shows the western side entrance, and the arch is surrounded by two towers, each with wide rooms, and it leads to a road that crosses the city from the north to the south. Nowadays, it is called Al-Wad, and it is called al-Amud adding to that other names like the gate of Nablus, Bab Damascus, and St. Stephen's Gate which is connected to a small museum, that includes the developments of Bab Al-Amoud, and an important part of the Roman street that falls below the current level of the door of the column [16].

The image of the gate of Al-Amud was processed and converted as a first stage to the digital Burin Line Engraving technique and then the deletion and addition processes came either by stone touches or using yellow and orange colors degrees and brown tones, Fig. 4.

The experimental side also dealt with Al-Nather Gate with the graphical study and digital processing of the door's fig. 5. which is one of the gates of Al-Aqsa Mosque inside the walls of the Old City of Jerusalem. It is located in the Islamic neighborhood in the western hallway of Al-Aqsa Mosque, and it was constructed during the Umayyad period. This gate also is made up of a wide and high entrance built with tapered stone arches, with a wooden door of two scrolls, surmounted by a copper strip, on the west.

Figure 4: "Bab Al-Amoud", Digital printing, 50 x 70 cm 2019

The entrance is fronted from this side by an arch that is pointed with a stone necklace, covered with a crossed vault, using the Blending Mode from the Layers menu. It has been focused on the entrance door and confirmed the aura of light in it symbolizing the lightness that comes with the fragrant of entering Al-Masjid Al-Aqsa. The set of yellow to dark brown colors and geometric circles and rectangles in purple at the bottom of the artwork were used.

2. The aesthetics of mosques' architecture in Jerusalem

The philosophy of constructing Jerusalem architecture is based on a single pattern, which is the great similarity between Islamic and Christian architecture, specifically, what is related to the use of inspiration to design domes in Christian churches and Islamic mosques linked to a common historical source. These designs use of the circle as a symbol of the sky, the square as a symbol of the earth, and the appraiser as a link between them both. In addition to that, the decoration was used to reinforce that the design of the domes were visual metaphors for the spiritual journey and the connection between human and divine worlds. There was also a purpose behind designing architectural spaces, whether in the Dome of the Rock, the Church of the Holy Sepulcher, or the subsequent design of the mosque of Aya Safiya in Turkey for the engineer Sinan.

Figure 5: Al-Nather Gate, Digital printing, 50 x 70 cm 2019

Dome of the Rock, Qubbat al-Sakhrah Mosque, Al-Aqsa Mosque has 15 domes that add a special luster, and are distributed in the vicinity of the mosque, where most of them were built during the Umayyad and Ayyubid period, and each dome has a different form and construction style. Some of these domes

are Domeseries, Dome of the Rock, and Dome of Al-Miraj. In this research, we will deal with a distinct model in Islamic domes named the Dome of the Rock, which is one part of Al-Aqsa Mosque that includes everything that is within Al-Aqsa wall.

It is also one of the most important Islamic mosques in Al-Quds city, Palestine, and the Islamic world, and one of the most beautiful buildings in the world. The Dome of the Rock is considered one of the most prominent Islamic architectural monuments adding to that considering it as the oldest Islamic building that remained conservative on its shape and decorations. The mosque and its dome were built by the Caliph Abdul Malik bin Marwan, and the Dome of the Rock is an octagonal building with four doors having another octagonal shape inside which is based on pillars and cylindrical columns. It also contains within it a circle with the writings "honorable rock," from which the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) lamed to the sky in the journey of Isra and Miraj [17].

The honorable Dome of the Rock is one of the most important Islamic landmarks in the World, and it represents the oldest model in Islamic architecture because of its stature and religious sanctity. Because of its artistic and aesthetic splendor that is folded up between its decoration fingerprints of Islamic civilization over its successive periods, it brought the attention and attentiveness of researchers, visitors and all people from all parts of the world. It has also been distinguished by the consistency and harmony between its architectural and decorative elements, even considered a masterpiece in architecture.

Through digital processing with Burin Line Engraving technique with geometric shapes overlapping in the artwork, these elements were processed and combined to transform the image of the Dome of the Rock Mosque into an artwork with a color processing in colors from yellow to dark brown, as the importance of designing the Dome of the Rock represented in fig. 6.

The building is characterized by a unique architectural touch, which is considered a distinctive and magnificent architectural mark, and it is considered as the most beautiful of these monuments at all according to the consensus of Architecture and art scientists, although influenced by the construction of Byzantine architecture prevailing at the time.

The Dome of the Rock is characterized by various motifs and the distinctive use of the Al-Thuluth calligraphy through the mosaic on the outer octagon part Fig. 7. Through the octagonal composition, the artwork has been processed in shades between light beige and dark brown as a result of overlapping colors through color schemes using Photoshop Blend Mode and through the color systems as observed in Fig. 8. As shown, it is a part of the building of Al-Qibli mosque which is part of Al-Aqsa Mosque and one of its monuments with a roofed building topped by a dome covered by a layer of lead, located in the south side of Al-Aqsa Mosque towards Al-Qiblah in which the name Al-Qibli came from. Caliph Omar ibn al-Khattab was the first one who commissioned to construct it when he opened Al-Quds in 15 AH corresponding 636 AD. It is the main Musala where the praying Muslims gather behind the imam on Friday prayers at Al-Aqsa Mosque.

3. Minarets in Al-Aqsa Mosque:

The minaret of Bab al-Ghawanmeh was named with this name as it is near to Bab al-Ghawanmeh, and it has also given the name of "Qala'un Lighthouse." It was renovated during the reign of the Mamluk Sultan Muhammad ibn Qalawun in 730 AH -1329 CE. It was also called the lighthouse of the Saraya because of its proximity to the Saraya building located outside Al-Aqsa Mosque, which was the

place of Governance Centre during the Mamluk era. Through this model, the interest of the researcher to the

Figure 6: The Dome of the Rock, Digital printing, 50 x 70 cm 2019

Figure 7: Aesthetics of the third line on the Dome of the Rock Mosque from the outside, Digital printing, 50 x 70 cm 2019

Figure 8: Al-Qibli mosque, Digital printing, 50 x 70 cm 2019

effects of digital technology is noted to show the aesthetic dimension of the technique of Burin Line Engraving as shown in Fig. 9. The researcher also relied on this artwork on the effect of the color overlay to show the color diversity of the design units, which it has in turn been given attractive aesthetic dimensions.

4. Dome of the Church of the Holy Sepulchre

Some scientists mentioned that churches built by the Knights Templar (Fursan al-Haykal) later was

influenced by the Islamic architectural style and the pattern of the Dome of the Rock, and it is clearly reflected in the Italian Castle of Del Monte.

Figure 9: The minaret of Bab al-Ghawanmeh, Digital printing, 50 x 70 cm 2019

The Emperor Constantine ordered to construct three churches, one above the Holy Sepulcher, the other above Golgotha and the third above the Grotto of the Cross, where the ground was paved to become parallel to the Holy Sepulcher. He also distributed around the tomb twenty marble pillars in a wide circle, surmounted by henayas and surrounded by a round wall, which turns in its four sides into two eastern, one left and the other to the east, with a third eastern opposite the large entrance. All of them are covered by a great dome that Bishop Aurushalim proposed to be covered in pure silver. This is known as the Church of the Holy Sepulcher, which took six years to be built, and it was completed in 335 AD [17].

It has also one of the most important domes in the Old City, the dome of the Church of the Holy Sepulcher, which shares the space and design with the Dome of the Rock Fig 10, where this artwork contains both the dome of the Church of the Holy Sepulcher, which is above the Holy Sepulcher and the Dome of Al-Aqsa Mosque. The great interest in the graphic processing was shown in terms of using color processors for the feature of Blending Mode from Layers menu, and also employing the technique of the digital Burin Line Engraving technique with the use of a number of postage stamps representing earlier periods of Palestine.

Figure 10: The dome of the Church of the Holy Sepulcher

Digital printing, 50 x 70 cm 2019

The study depended on the al-Nurani side in the artistic work to express that interfaith communication between religions in spiritual symbolism, and whatever the constraints that stand in the way, but it will not prevent that relationship in the peaceful coexistence between religions away from blind intolerance. Therefore, the researcher adopted in the digital processing of that artistic work through those set of colors extending from yellow to dark brown as well as the values of black and white, which reinforced the solidity of the artistic composition. In this work, the research also relied on a typographic aspect of Arabic texts in the symbolism of the Arabism of these holy places.

5. Sabils in Al-Haram Al-Qudsi:

Fountain of Qayt Bay, Sabil Qaitbay Al-Aqsa Mosque contains approximately 16 fountains used for drinking and ablution, the most important of which is Qaitbay, a famous water fountain, located inside Al-Aqsa Mosque campus opposite Al-Mutahrah Gate. Al-Sabeel was built on the northwestern end of a large terrace with the same name, and it has also a niche in the south side. It was built by King Ashraf Abulnasr Inal (860 AH), and then renovated by King Ashraf Qaytbay "Al Sabeel" in 887 AH - 1482 AD after its demolition, leaving only the well, known in his name. Ottoman Sultan Abdul Majid II renovated it in 1330 AH-1912 AD, which consists of a square building surmounted by a dome with prominent leafy motifs.

In the digital processing of Sabil Qaitbay fig 11 as one of the most important and most beautiful fountains in the city, the researcher relied on the digital processing of

Figure 11: Sabil Qaitbay, Digital printing, 50 x 70 cm 2019

the image of Al-Sabeel with digital Burin Line Engraving technique and then relied on the merging of a number of layers that reached more than 40 layers through the feature of Blending mode from the list of Layers. The researcher also used the red color at the bottom of the artwork symbolizing the threat of Judaization on those monuments of Jerusalem, which record the Islamic nation's memory since the first century of the Hegira and so far.

6. Old City and the Road of Suffering:

The Old City includes Islamic and Christian holy sites, most notably Al-Aqsa Mosque, the Church of the Holy Sepulcher, and the Wall of Buraq, and a number of lanes, alleys, and Jerusalem markets. The road of suffering comes in Fig. 12. as one of the important paths within the Old City. It is the path that Jesus Christ, peace be upon him, walked through from the moment of his judgment until the implementation of the crucifixion, according to the Christian faith.

The road consists of fourteen stages, each representing a chapter of his suffering, and the stages of the road begin near Al-Asbat gate, a place where Christ was presented before the Supreme Council of Jews and the Roman governor Pilate, who ruled in his crucifixion, until he was buried in the church of Al-Qiyamah in the Old City of Jerusalem. The first nine stages of the road lie outside the framework of the Church of

Figure 12: The Road of Suffering, Digital printing, 50 x 70 cm 2019

the Holy Sepulcher, and the last five within it, and the researcher in the artwork reshapes the old architectural environment in a contemporary experimental vision. The researcher in that vision adds from his experiences and practices in design and graphic arts to achieve new additions to the digital graphical artistic work through the use of digital techniques. He also reshaped the visual vision of the road of suffering using digital Burin Line Engraving technique and green color as a symbol of peace

and goodness and dark brown at the bottom as a symbol of what does this path carry from the scenes of Jesus Christ's sufferings.

In all stages of the creative process in the artistic experiment, the research relied on Fine Art formulation to produce printed artwork loaded with aesthetic, artistic, and expressive values, through digital printing on canvas, which is medium thickness cotton using a machine that uses fixed color inks.

The research addressed a proposed design of the cover and the internal pages of the Encyclopedia of Antiquities of Bayt Al-Maqdis as a viable graphic project, through the artistic product of the Antiquities of Jerusalem as illustrations in that proposed encyclopedia. The researcher relied on the Adobe Illustrator program to design the cover in Fig. 13. using one of the researcher's works for an architectural scene of the Dome of the Rock Mosque, which has been digitally processed, by digital Burin Line Engraving technique.

Figure 13: The cover of the Encyclopedia of Antiquities of Bayt Al-Maqdis, 21 x 27.5 cm 2019

The research also dealt with the design of a number of internal pages of the proposed encyclopedia Fig. 14 using a number of designs for the architectural places in Jerusalem, such as domes, minarets, and the road of suffering in the Old City, using bilingualism through Arabic and Latin typography. The researcher used various Arts processing in the design to serve as an artistic language characterized by communication and civilization extension through the authenticity of the past of the city of Jerusalem.

Figure 14: page of the Encyclopedia of Antiquities of Bayt Al-Maqdis, 21 x 27.5 cm 2019

As a result, the study used part of the design of An-Nather gate in a rectangular vertical shape in the right side with both orange and green colors, and also black and dark red. The design also was compatible with the golden ratio in the largest side containing the typography, and also the lower third that contains 5 of the artworks of the city of Jerusalem.

III. RESULTS

1. Benefit from digital technology in art and design, which contributes to the creation of contemporary visual and art solutions.
2. Consolidate the concept of scientific, artistic and technical exchange between contemporary technology and fine art.
3. Contribute to the creation of graphic artworks that have a cultural, artistic and social dimension through the development of a contemporary graphic vision for image processing.
4. Show interest in finding visual solutions of a philosophical nature in the artworks, which adds aesthetic dimension and attracts the recipient.

IV. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The research recommends the importance of using digital technology in optical processing to record architectural monuments threatened by sabotage.
2. The research recommends supporting digital art printing exhibitions and workshops for artists and graphic design students.
3. The researcher calls through this research to preserve the architectural and archaeological heritage of the monuments of Bayt Al-Maqdis.

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